

Optimizing Hot Plate Welding Parameters for Enhanced Welding Strength in Plastic Cylinders

Peyman Hashemi^{1, *}, Amin Ghalenoei², Keivan Amidpour¹

¹Research & Development Department, Smart Group Co., Istanbul, Turkey

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Azad University, Abadan, Iran

Email address:

peyman-hashemi@smart.org.tr (Peyman Hashemi), amin.ghalenoei@iau.ac.ir (Amin Ghalenoei),

kayhan-turan@smart.org.tr (Keivan Amidpour)

*Corresponding author

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Abstract: Hot plate welding is a critical technique in the production of plastic parts, where precise control of welding parameters directly affects the quality and cost-effectiveness of the final product. In this study, we explore the theory of plastic welding, providing a detailed explanation of the process and the specific procedures employed in our production line, along with the equipment used. To identify the most influential factors on weld strength, three key parameters, melting time, melting temperature of the tube, and melting temperature of the plate were selected for analysis. A dedicated test method was designed, and optimization was performed using the One-Factor-At-a-Time (OFAT) approach and Minitab software. The results indicate that higher melting temperatures and prolonged melting times, within an appropriate range, enhance polymer chain diffusion, leading to increased weld strength in cylindrical plastic vessels. By integrating theoretical insights with experimental findings, this study provides optimized welding parameters that significantly improve the welding quality. The outcomes offer valuable guidance for achieving superior weld strength while maintaining production efficiency in plastic manufacturing processes.

Keywords: Hot Plate Welding Process, Weld Strength, Optimization, Melting Temperature

1. Introduction

Today, plastics are ubiquitous, owing to their numerous advantages, including the ease of recycling and reuse. They have increasingly supplanted metal parts across various sectors, including packaging, automotive, and aerospace industries. A key attribute of plastics is their flexibility, which enables the design and fabrication of complex components. However, certain products are too intricate to be cast as a single piece. This necessitates the production of sub-components, which are then assembled with the main part. Among the various methods of assembly, welding stands out as a prevalent technique. There exist several welding types, such as "hot tool, hot gas, extrusion, implant induction, and implant resistance welding," each suited for different applications and requirements [1, 2].

The efficiency and cost-effectiveness of hot plate welding have solidified its status as a leading method for joining thermoplastics. In this technique, plastic components are heated to their melting point through direct contact with a heat source. Once the specific surfaces reach the desired molten state, the heat source is withdrawn from the welding area. Immediately after, a controlled amount of pressure is applied to effectively merge the parts. This pressure is maintained throughout the cooling phase to ensure a strong bond (as depicted in Figure 1). Hot plate welding is particularly adept at handling thermoplastics and involves three critical stages: a) Melting of the contact surfaces, b) Joining the heated surfaces, and c) Cooling and solidification to form a durable joint. The protocols and standards for this welding technique are thoroughly detailed in [3].

Figure 1. Schematics of Hot-plate Welding Process, [4].

Proper functioning of the welding machine is essential for ensuring the quality of the manufactured product and achieving customer satisfaction. Inadequate welding of plastic parts can lead to multiple issues. Firstly, improperly welded products are likely to fail customer-specific tests. Additionally, they may not withstand the non-destructive testing conducted in the factory on all products before packaging and dispatch. This could result in the products being deemed defective and discarded as waste. Furthermore, even if a product sporadically passes all these tests, there remains a risk of weak welds failing during transportation. Such incidents not only amount to product damage but also, in a manner of speaking, involve damage to the producer's reputation. The strength and reliability of the welding process thus become very important to maintain the integrity of the product and sustain the standing of the producer in the marketplace.

Numerous studies have focused on the hot-plate welding process. In their research, Shim and Kim [5] applied this technique to bond acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) polymers using a "lap-joint configuration". Their findings indicated that both the plate contact time and temperature significantly influence the bond strength, with the key determinant being the adequate flow of the molten polymer, essential for developing robust joint strength. The study explored hot-plate temperatures ranging from 180°C to 260°C, in conjunction with various contact times spanning from 10 to 60 minutes. It showed that the value of the optimum bonding strength could be consistently achieved at 260°C for variations in contact time. The variation of the bond strength with the various time scales considered showed an increase from approximately 8 MPa to 11 MPa.

In their study, Watson and Murch [6] examined the hot plate welding technique on three distinct injection-molded thermoplastics: polypropylene (PP), high-impact polystyrene (PS), and poly(phenylene oxide). They assessed the success of the welding by conducting tensile strength tests. The findings of the research made it clear that the hot plate welding process succeeded with the three materials, although the degrees of sensitivity against changes in the process parameters were different. It was established that during the heating stage, both the hot plate temperature and time are important factors in the production of quality welds, whereas changes in the consolidation phase parameters are relatively less sensitive.

Cylindrical metallic and plastic-made structures are widely used in equipment design due to their lightweight nature,

strength-to-weight ratio, and durability, making them essential in industries such as aerospace, automotive, construction, and consumer products [7–13]. Najand et al. [14] investigated the effect of different production parameters on the buckling strength of cylindrical containers produced from extruded tubes. Their main research objective was to examine variations in such critical parameters as the temperature of the water in the vacuum calibrator, the temperature of the cooling water in the vacuum tank, the wall thickness of the cylinder, and the thermal gradient in the extrusion mold. Furthermore, factors such as degreasing and printing, stress relief, and the time elapsed since the production of the pipes were also considered. Two methods, "One Factor at a Time (OFAT)" and Design of Experiments (DOE), were used to determine the effects of these parameters on buckling strength. A regression relationship was developed using Mini Tab software, allowing the optimal values for these parameters to be calculated.

Davis et al. [15] investigated the importance of understanding the mechanical properties of parts fabricated by additive manufacturing (AM), more precisely through polymer extrusion (PE). The research demonstrated how the processing parameters of the extruder speed and temperature of the extruder have a strong impact on the weld strength between the extruded filaments. They apply a "trouser tear" Mode III fracture experiment and optical microscopy for the evaluation of fracture toughness of single welds, revealing the relationship between welding strength and printing parameters in PE-AM.

Walesa et al. [16] investigate the technique of welding by round belt hot plate made of thermoplastic elastomers, more precisely polyurethane, which is usually used in industrial machines for belt transmission. Their study is aimed at designing an automatic welding machine, focusing on understanding the thermomechanical properties of the material and the physical phenomena during welding. They detail the standard welding cycle and the temperature distribution through each phase, providing key insights necessary for optimizing the welding process and its automation.

Novakovic et al. [17] investigate the behavior of "high-density polyethylene (HDPE)" in the context of "hot plate welding (HPW)" applications. They focus on thermal expansion in HDPE, which can impact cycle times and equipment performance. Through experiments with varying HDPE samples and process parameters, they observe size changes and develop a mathematical model for thermal expansion under different conditions. Their study highlights the temperature-dependent nature of industrial guidelines for pressure during the Matching stage and provides a visual representation of HDPE behavior with temperature variations. In another work, Novakovic and Kashkoush [18] conducted a study on the material displacement of "high-density polyethylene (HDPE)" during the Matching stage of the "hot plate welding (HPW)" process. They developed mathematical models that establish the connection between key process parameters, including force, temperature, time, and surface area size. These models, based on collected data, offer valuable tools for optimizing process parameters and

equipment specifications in HDPE production.

Wübbecke *et al.* [19] investigated residual stresses and mechanical features of polypropylene samples welded by hot plate and containing %0.1 weight of carbon black. They found out that the more the displacement during the joint increased, the more the residual stress increased. They also discovered a correlation between the displacement during the joint and the alpha spherulite size. Their application of WAXS, however gave no clarity about the beta phase on the samples.

The current research aims to assess the impact of hot plate welding machine parameters on the welding strength of a plastic sample cut from a cylindrical drum. To achieve this, the study begins by identifying the key adjustable parameters of the welding machine that exert the most significant influence on weld quality and establishing their allowable ranges. Subsequently, through the application of the "Design of Experiments (DOE)" methodology and Minitab software, the necessary experiments are defined to examine the effects of these parameters. The study then employs regression analysis on the experimental data to establish relationships that elucidate the individual impacts of these parameters on welding strength, filling a notable gap in previous research in this field.

2. Theory of Plastic Welding

Contemporary approaches to characterizing welding processes encompass two distinct methodologies: the empirical analysis of thermal behavior and the application of reptation theory. The latter, a concept originated by DeGennes in the 1970s, scrutinizes the interactions among polymer chains when subjected to heat. This theory posits that these chains are restricted within a virtual tubular space due to the intertwining with nearby chains. Upon the melting of the polymer interface, chain ends are liberated, allowing them to take on new positions. These liberated chain ends are designated as "minor chains." An illustrative model of this dynamic, is depicted in Figure 2 [20]. In due course, there comes a moment referred to as the 'reptation time' when the polymer chain completely abandons its original structure, leading to the movement of its mass center. The duration of the reptation time is determined by a scaling equation (Equation 1).

$$T_{rep} = \frac{R_g^2}{D_s} \tag{1}$$

Equation 1 relates the time it takes for a polymer chain to diffuse its own radius of gyration, with R_g representing the radius of gyration and D_s the diffusion coefficient. This time is pivotal because, prior to it, polymer chain end diffusion does not follow Fick's law, complicating the average diffusion distance calculation. Once this reptation time is achieved, normal diffusion resumes, and Fick's law applies. This concept is critical to understanding strength development in polymers, where the strength scales with the interpenetration of diffusing chains as described by Wool *et al.* [21]. The

early stage, non-linear diffusion is further characterized by Wool *et al* [20], offering a statistical approach to model the concentration profile and interpenetration depth over time.

$$X(t) = \left(\frac{3\pi^{\frac{1}{4}}}{32^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) a^{\frac{1}{2}} (Dt)^{\frac{1}{4}} \tag{2}$$

Figure 2. Polymer chain diffusion from interface wetting to achieving radius of gyration distance, [20].

Figure 3. Strength linearly correlates with $t_m^{1/4}$ across differing diffusion coefficients at constant temperature molten interfaces, demonstrating accelerated polymer chain diffusion at higher temperatures., [22].

The Equation 2 highlights the role of a , the monomer's average length, and D , the curvilinear diffusion coefficient, in understanding molten polymers' non-Fickian dynamics. However, the nebulous characteristics of D render it less useful for analyzing chain diffusion. Equation 2 shows how the material's strength relates to the melt time, becoming important when the latter reaches the reptation time: the average interpenetration distance then is of the order of the radius of gyration, so the material has become homogeneous and the weld has regained its original strength. The reptation theory, therefore indicates that the weld interface must be kept at or above the melt temperature for at least the length of time represented by the reptation time for adequate strength to develop, since times in melt longer than this provide no further

increase in strength. These principles are visually summarized in Figure 3, where strength is plotted against $t_m^{\frac{1}{4}}$ across varying diffusion coefficients. Elevated healing temperatures quicken the attainment of inherent weld strength, with a linear representation of strength against $X(t)$ converging all data to a single trajectory, where $X(t)$ equals the gyration radius. Wool et al. [21] explore molecular weight's role in polymer movement, revealing a time and weight-dependent power law. These models, while accurate, omit temperature's role and are limited to similar polymers, not reflecting the full welding process. Practical measures often rely on direct bond strength testing linked to operational parameters, yet these methods miss underlying polymer interactions, necessitating tailored empirical models for each unique welding scenario.

In the given scenario, Ezekoye et al [22] consider two polyethylene pipe sections being fused with a doped polyethylene coupling, typically seen in Radio Frequency (RF) welding systems, as their model. This is depicted in Figure 4, with the pipe having a wall thickness of 1 cm and a length of 10 cm. Given the small wall thickness relative to the pipe's inner radius (13.2 cm) and the even temperature distribution across the transverse direction, a one-dimensional approach is deemed suitable, ignoring curvature effects. They employ a control volume finite difference code for this one-dimensional welding simulation [23]. The appropriateness of this radial temperature distribution simplification can be assessed by

considering the pipe's Biot number, which balances convective against conductive resistance (Equation 3).

$$Bi_L = \frac{hL}{k} \tag{3}$$

Using an empirical formula for natural convection [24], the heat transfer coefficient is set at $5W/m^2K$, with the characteristic dimension (L) being half of the pipe wall's thickness. The minimum thermal conductivity of PE is 0.25 W/mK [25], leading to a cautiously calculated Biot number of 0.1. This suggests that the main resistance is due to convection, making a one-dimensional analysis suitable. The boundary conditions have been established accordingly (Equation 4).

$$T(x = 0, t) = T_\infty \tag{4}$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right|_{x=1} = 0$$

For all types of welding, the essential action that creates a weld zone is applying heat to the junction of two materials. Despite different welding methods (like ultrasonic, hotplate, induction, butt, spin, etc.) sharing this core principle, the energy equation is crucial for the initial approximation of a weld's development (Equation 5).

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho u_i C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) + Q_0''' H_s(x - x_L) - \frac{hP}{A_c} (T - T_\infty) \tag{5}$$

Figure 4. Model pipe system schematic: Displays an axial section of a pipe wall with a heat zone, convective boundary conditions along its length, and a semi-infinite boundary at the opposite end, including dimensions., [22].

In "induction/implant welding", boundary conditions are crucial due to the volumetric heat source localized within the filler material, requiring an assessment of contact resistance affected by joining pressure. This resistance, originating from surface roughness, diminishes with deformation and is highly responsive to the pressure applied (Equation 6).

$$h_c = 956.82 + 0.25625 \times P \tag{6}$$

Derived from Marotta and Fletcher [26], the model correlates a slight linear increase in contact conductance (W/m^2K) with interface pressure (kPa), specifically at 950 kPa for a conductance of $1200 W/m^2K$. As temperature rises, plastics transition from semicrystalline to amorphous, reducing contact resistance, which potentially complicates the energy equation without convective terms. Initially, this complexity is excluded, and the focus is on variable specific "heat capacity that accounts for the heat of fusion", following the approach by Woo et al. [25] (Equation 7).

$$c_p = 2250 \left[1 + 5.5 \exp(-a(T - 135)^2) \right] \left[\frac{J}{kg^\circ C} \right] \tag{7}$$

$$a = 0.005 \quad (T \leq 135^\circ C)$$

$$a = 0.05 \quad (T > 135^\circ C)$$

Figure 5 illustrates this relationship, while Woo *et al.* furnish a formula for thermal conductivity applicable to both melt and solid phases (Equation 8).

$$k_p = 0.17 + 5(\rho_p - 0.9) - 0.001 \times T \quad (T \leq 135^\circ C) \quad (8)$$

$$k_p = 0.25 \quad (T > 135^\circ C)$$

Thermal conductivity's relationship to temperature is depicted in Figure 5. Thermal stability is a concern, as high temperatures degrade polymer chains, reducing or destroying weld strength. Polyethylene, for example, must not exceed 260°C [27] during welding to avoid damage. Fast-heating welding methods, like Friction Welding (FW) or electrofusion, risk exceeding this temperature. Wool *et al.* [25] describe chain pullout and fracture as failure modes, with pullout stress depending on healing time and molecular weight, illustrated for polystyrene in Figure 30 [25] and for polyethylene in Figure 3. Increasing weld temperatures correlate with stronger welds at consistent healing times. The research goal is to create a comprehensive model that predicts weld strength based on polymer chain dynamics, contrasting with reptation theory's static approach. Green [28] outlines how the diffusion coefficient's temperature dependency is critical to this dynamic welding process (Equation 9).

Figure 5. Polyethylene's specific heat is steady, rising only at its 135°C melt point; thermal conductivity drops linearly in solids and holds at 0.25 W/m°C melted., [25].

$$\log \left[\frac{D_{rep}(T)}{D_{rep}(T_{ref})} \times \frac{T_{ref}}{T} \right] = \frac{B}{(T_{ref} - T_0)} - \frac{B}{(T - T_0)} \quad (9)$$

Equation 9 utilizes Vogel-Fulcher constants along with a baseline diffusion coefficient, setting B at 1225°C and T_0 at -112°C [29], to simulate the impact of temperature on polymer diffusion. The reference self-diffusion coefficient for polyethylene is $8 \times 10^{-16} m^2/s$ at 176°C for a molecular

weight of 250,000 [30]. Diffusion distances align with the polyethylene's chain radius of gyration, R_g , approximately 1000 for the given molecular weight [31, 32]. Due to small diffusion lengths, the interface temperature remains effectively constant, serving as the diffusion temperature. The diffusion coefficient is time-averaged for the welding interface temperature, determining an "equivalent diffusion coefficient" for the welding process (Equation 10).

$$\bar{D}_s = \frac{1}{t_{m,max}} \int_0^{t_{m,max}} D_s(t_m, T) dt_m \quad (10)$$

An equivalent reptation time is computed using the equivalent coefficient via Equation 1, with the maximum strength percentage at $t_{m,max}$ being specified as follows (Equation 11):

$$\frac{\sigma(t_{m,max})}{\sigma_{max}} = \left(\frac{t_{m,max}}{\tau_{rep}} \right)^{1/4} = \left(\frac{t_{m,max} \bar{D}_s}{R_g^2} \right)^{1/4} \quad (11)$$

When heal time surpasses reptation time (derived from the equivalent diffusion coefficient), strength reaches the maximum inherent strength. This welding strength prediction method simply incorporates variable interface temperatures, affecting polymer chain diffusion rates and reptation time.

3. Plastic Welding Steps

In the hot plate welding process for plastic parts, the operation is segmented into five distinct stages. Each stage is marked by unique physical phenomena during heat transfer. It's possible to approximately predict the temperature distribution across these stages. A crucial aspect of this process is the plasticization of the part's end, which is essential for initiating chemical reactions and physical interactions among macromolecules, a key factor in the welding process. The success of the plasticization stage is critically important to the next stages of welding, especially in fostering the creation of strong joints during the cooling phase, where durable molecular bonds are formed between plastic parts.

3.1. Adaption

The welding process starts with aligning the ends of plastic parts, as illustrated in Figure 6. This step involves heating and melting the flat surfaces of the parts upon contact with a hot plate set at temperature T_p , enabling the parts to reach the welding temperature T_w . The choice of T_w is critical, varying with the type of polymer; exceeding the degradation temperature can damage the material. In some polymers, higher welding temperatures can improve joint strength.

Figure 6. In the hot plate welding's adaption phase for plastic parts, the setup includes the plastic part (1), shaped grip (2), and hot plate (3), with key variables such as adaption force F_m , velocity v_m , temperatures T_p , T_w , T_0 , and distances p , h . The process involves heat transfers denoted as Q_{p3-1} , Q_{p1} , Q_{r1} , Q_{r3} , Q_{c1} , and Q_{c3} . [16].

In this stage, the specially shaped clamps clamp the ends of the plastic parts and move them with a speed v_m , towards the hot plate. In contact with the hot plate, the parts experience a force F_m , which plasticizes and partially melts them. In this way, the process allows the surfaces of the parts to take the shape of the hot plate, which is strongly dependent on the temperature of the plate.

Since the plastic parts are being heated, their temperature rises longitudinally, defining two critical lengths: p , such that the temperature rises above the welding threshold T_w , and h , where the temperature exceeds the base temperature T_0 . The heat transfer observed includes conduction, convection, and radiation. Conduction within the plastic parts and contact conduction between the parts and hot plate are dominant, while radiation is less significant due to lower process temperatures. Convection's role is minimized in this scenario.

During the alignment phase, the plastic parts are aligned with each other parallel to each other and perpendicularly to the central axis, putting them in place for bonding. It eliminates imperfections and roughness from cutting, enhancing joint quality. Uniform heat transfer across the parts' surface is established, replacing point thermal conduction, convection, and radiation through material cavities (Figure 7) with stable, whole surface conduction (Figure 8).

Figure 7. Heating the unadapted plastic part 1 with the hot plate 2 involves contact points 3, cavities with hot gases 4, and heat transfers Q_{p3-1} , Q_{r3} , and Q_{c3} . [16]

Figure 8. The adapted plastic part's surface is heated by the hot plate, consisting of the plastic part 1 and the hot plate 2, with heat transfer denoted as Q_{p3-1} . [16].

3.2. Melting Step

In the melting step (Figure 9), plastic part ends 1 are pressed against the hot plate 3 with shaped grips 2 exerting a force F_h . This step increases the effect of convection Q_{c1} and radiation Q_{r1} due to a larger heated area, introducing conduction between the plastic part's surface and grips Q_{p1-2} . Key objectives include extending the plasticized distance p for optimal joining, with an incidental increase in distance h . The force F_h , lower than the initial force F_m (10%-20% of F_m), is crucial to avoid excessive material loss and displacement, which can negatively affect the joint. However, sufficient F_h force is necessary to prevent material outflow, aided by the thermal expansion of the plastic part.

Figure 9. The adapted plastic part's surface is heated by the hot plate, consisting of the plastic part 1 and the hot plate 2, with heat transfer denoted as Q_{p3-1} . [16].

3.3. Hot Plate Removal Step

During the hot plate removal step, the hot plate is extracted from between the plastic part ends (Figure 10). The plastic part 1, slightly moved by shaped grips 2, minimally clears the hot plate. This action ends the heating, necessitating a brief removal to prevent energy loss through convection Q_{c1} and radiation Q_{r1} from the part's surfaces. It's crucial to control the temperature drop, especially in the plasticized areas, to

maintain welding temperature above T_w , highlighting the need for a quick removal.

Figure 10. The hot plate removal step in welding includes the plastic part 1, shaped grip 2, temperatures T_p , T_w , T_0 , plasticize distance p , heated region length h , with heat transfers Q_{p1-2} , Q_{p1} , Q_{r1} , and Q_{c1} . [16].

3.4. Welding Step

During the welding step, the ends of the plastic part 1 are held by shaped grips 2 and brought together, leading to the fusion of their surfaces (Figure 11). This step is pivotal for material bonding, characterized mainly by two phenomena: chemical reactions among hydrocarbon molecules and mechanical interactions between macromolecules, resulting in their fusion. The welding step requires balancing a short duration with a low welding velocity v_j . A brief duration, paired with relatively high v_j , is advantageous for minimizing energy loss through convection Q_{c1} and radiation Q_{r1} . However, both the welding velocity v_j and force F_j should be minimized to prevent excessive distortion in the plasticized region.

Figure 11. In hot plate welding's welding step: plastic part 1, shaped grip 2, forces F_j , v_j , temperatures T_p , T_w , T_0 , distances p , h , and heat transfers Q_{p1-2} , Q_{p1} , Q_{r1} , Q_{c1} . [16].

3.5. Cooling Step

In hot plate welding's cooling Step (Figure 12), the plastic part 1 ends are pressed together, cooling down to ambient temperature T_0 through air interaction. This Step involves temperature equalization by contact conduction, ongoing chemical and mechanical interactions within macromolecules, and heat transfer predominantly through conduction Q_{p1} , with natural convection Q_{c1} and radiation Q_{r1} to the environment. The Step's length is determined by the time it takes for the part to reach T_0 . Generally, the cooling Step is the lengthiest part of the welding process.

Figure 12. During hot plate welding's cooling phase: plastic part 1, shaped grip 2, cooling force F_c , temperatures T_p , T_w , T_0 , and heat transfers Q_{p1} , Q_{r1} , Q_{c1} [16].

Figure 13. Plastic cylindrical Drum.

Figure 14. Welding Machine.

4. Experimental Investigations

This section details the functioning of the hot plate welding machine and the process used to create the test specimens. Additionally, it introduces the test machine, providing an in-depth explanation of its operation. Then, experimental procedures are described in detail, and data recording methods are explained thoroughly.

4.1. Description of the Welding Machine

Figure 13 displays an image of a cylindrical drum, which is composed of three distinct sections: the bottom part, the polymer tube, and the top part. The assembly of these components is accomplished through a three-step process using a hot plate welding machine, specifically designed and manufactured by Queen Pack Co., as depicted in Figure 14. The production method for the tube, created using an extruder machine, is detailed in reference [14]. In addition, the top and bottom components of the drum are molded using a plastic injection molding process.

In the first step, the bottom part and the tube are placed in a fixture: the tube is held in place by a clamp with a semicircular section, while a circular ring-type fixture is used for the bottom part. Next, both the bottom part and the tube are moved towards a hot plate, which is coated with a non-stick layer. They are pressed against both sides of the hot plate, adhering to specific time and torque parameters (termed the melting time and melting torque). Following this, the bottom part and tube are separated from the hot plate, which is then lowered. In the third step, the bottom part and the tube are joined together, using a predetermined torque (the welding torque) and for a set duration (the welding time). After this period, the clamp is removed from the tube, and the semi-welded tube is extracted from the machine. These steps are repeated to weld the top part to the tube, completing the full drum.

Once the welding process is completed, the efficiency of the welding machine is evaluated in two phases, utilizing two non-destructive tests applied to every manufactured product. Post-processing in the hot plate welding machine, the newly formed plastic drum is permitted to return to ambient temperature. Subsequently, it's placed in a device known as a back-breaker

(illustrated in Figure 15). Here, the drum is positioned horizontally and inflated with high-pressure air. While rotating around its axis, two levers on opposite sides of the tube exert pressure near the weld joints. Should the welding be of substandard quality, resulting in inadequate bonding between the tube and its top or bottom part, a crack may form at the weld point. This would lead to a drop in the internal air pressure and trigger the device's alarm. A drum that successfully passes this test is automatically removed from the testing machine and proceeds to the next stage of quality assessment.

Figure 15. Non-destructive weld strength testing machine: back-breaker.

After successfully completing the test in the back-breaker, the next phase involves placing the drum vertically in a water tank. The drum is then refilled with high-pressure air, and the internal pressure is closely monitored. If, after a specific duration, the pressure inside the drum drops below a predetermined threshold, this triggers the unit's alarm, indicating a potential leak in the welds. Additionally, the water tank serves a dual purpose. In the event of a leak, air bubbles escaping from the drum will rise and condense in the water. This visual cue helps in precisely identifying the location of the leak.

Apart from the non-destructive tests, there is one more destructive test to check the body, bottom part, top part of the drum and the welds between the parts. This test corresponds to the "Electronic Code of Federal Regulations (eCFR)". <https://www.ecfr.gov>. This test is represented by selecting random drums from the batch of the produced drums, which are filled with water at 25°C. These drums are dropped from 120 cm in three different ways: firstly, a vertically dropped drum onto the bottom part, secondly, a drum dropped inclined to hit the corner of the bottom part, and lastly, a horizontally dropped drum that will hit the side of the container. After these drop tests, the drums should not show any cracks or leakages, thereby giving assurance of the drums quality and safety.

4.2. Test Method

The hot plate welding machine is equipped with 20 adjustable parameters, each playing a crucial role in optimizing the machine's performance. Fine-tuning these

parameters is key to ensuring the quality of the final product, particularly in terms of its ability to pass the tests described earlier. Reviewing the QC documents have identified three parameters as having the most significant impact on the assembly process of the top and bottom parts onto the tube. These critical parameters are the melting temperature of the tube, the melting temperature of the part (either bottom or top), and the melting time. Adjusting these parameters accurately is essential for achieving the desired quality and strength in the welded joints of the final product.

An experiment has been devised to evaluate the impact of certain parameters on the weld quality, drawing inspiration from the back-breaking test. The initial step of this experiment involves creating a sample, which is done by cutting a piece from a randomly chosen product on the production line, as illustrated in Figure 16. Subsequently, this sample is placed horizontally within a structure equipped with two jaws. The arrangement ensures that parts of both the bottom part and the tube are securely clamped within these jaws, while the area beneath the weld is deliberately left unoccupied. This setup, as shown in Figure 17, is critical for specifically assessing the integrity and strength of the weld in the experimental context.

Figure 16. Samples cut for testing.

Figure 17. Designed fixture to hold sample for the weld strength test.

The custom-made fixture, along with the sample, is inserted into the GOTECH device. Details about this device can be found in Table 1 and its visual representation is shown in Figure 18. To facilitate the experiments, the device's upper jaw has been modified: it now includes a lever with a semicircular cross-section, boasting a radius of 4 cm. The GOTECH device features a stationary upper plate, while its lower plate

is designed to move vertically. The arrangement of the test fixture is such that when the lower plate ascends, the lever applies force onto the tube, specifically targeting the area adjacent to the bottom part. This setup allows for precise measurement of the force exerted on the weld area by the lever, as recorded by the instrument.

Table 1. Technical specifications of Gotech.

Parameter	Description
Capacity (optional)	10kN
Unit (switchable)	Kgf, lbf, N, kN, kPa, Mpa
Load accuracy	Within $\pm 1\%$
Test space (L \times W \times H)	600 \times 600 \times 600mm
Speed accuracy	$\pm 0.5\%$
Dimension (W \times D \times H)	138 \times 60 \times 208 cm
Weight (approx.)	510 kg

Figure 18. Gotech Testing Machine.

To explore how various parameters impact welding strength, a two-phase testing approach was implemented. Initially, the first phase involved an in-depth examination of each parameter independently, utilizing the One Factor At A Time (OFAT) method. Subsequently, the second phase focused on assessing the collective influence of all parameters through the Design of Experiments (DOE) method.

4.3. Experimental Design Method

To assess the impact of the performance of the hot plate welding machine, three key parameters were chosen for experimental analysis using MiniTab software. These parameters include the tube melting temperature, the bottom plate melting temperature, and the melting time. We provided MiniTab with the variation ranges of these parameters, detailed in Table 2. Employing the BOX-Bencken method for experimental design, we set the number of center points at the default value of 2 and conducted one repetition of the experiments. This approach resulted in the production of 30

test samples, divided into two batches of 15. From each sample, four identical sectors were extracted and tested in the machine.

Table 2. The range of Selected parameters.

Range	Parameter
200-250	melting T of tube ($^{\circ}$ C)
150-240	melting T of bottom plate ($^{\circ}$ C)
6-10	melting time (s)

4.4. Test Procedure

In this study, we explored the impact of various elements on the welding strength in hot plate welding machine products. These elements can either individually or collectively influence the outcome. Notably, the adverse impact of one factor might be offset by the positive influence of another. We examined the influence of each factor in isolation and in combination with others. For singular factor analysis, we employed the classic "One Factor At a Time (OFAT) method". However, to assess the combined effects of these factors, we faced the challenge of an excessively high number of required tests using traditional approaches. To address this, we implemented the Design of Experiments (DOE) method, significantly reducing the number of tests needed. Section 5.1 details tests conducted via the OFAT method, while section 5.2 describes tests carried out using the DOE method.

In this study involving Queen Pack Co., a drum manufacturing company, we scrutinized the default settings of their hot plate welding machine. These settings are notably more stringent than the values we're considering. This is because they not only need to pass all standard tests but also must satisfy customer expectations. We initially applied these default settings in our tests. Our examinations of the factory's completed products revealed an exceptionally high weld strength. This strength was so significant that, in every instance, when force was applied, the tube would thin and ultimately break before the weld did, as illustrated in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Samples that are torn from the tube part.

In the default mode, the settings for each parameter are as follows: the melting time is set to 13 seconds, the tube's melting temperature is 340° C, and the bottom part's melting

temperature is 345°C. To evaluate the weld strength in the initial section, we produced three samples for each condition. From each sample, we extracted four sections, each in a

different direction. The dimensions of the finished product are depicted in Figure 20.

Figure 20. Dimensions of the manufactured product.

5. Experiment Results and Analyses

This section details the experimental findings and their analysis, structured into two distinct segments. Initially, we explored how various influential parameters affect welding strength by employing the traditional One-Factor-At-A-Time (OFAT) method. Based on quality assurance documents, we identified three parameters with the most significant impact from a broader set of adjustable factors. We first assessed the impact of each parameter independently, followed by an examination of their collective effect. To facilitate this, we defined the parameters’ range in MiniTab software. This tool helped us ascertain the requisite number of tests and specify the parameters’ values.

5.1. Traditional OFAT Method

During the initial part of the research, we mainly focused on assessing the effects of three specific parameters on welding strength, with each parameter studied individually. These parameters are the melting time, the melting temperature of the bottom part, and the melting temperature of the tube. The chosen range for each parameter extends from its minimum value, at which point no welding occurs between the base and the tube, to its maximum value, where the weld remains intact and the tube does not break during testing. The specific ranges selected for each parameter are detailed in Table 2.

As outlined in earlier sections, four segments are cut from each sample, one from each side. If any of these four segments breaks during testing, it indicates that the sample’s weld has

failed under the specified conditions. In such instances, the welding strength attributed to that sample is calculated as the average of the maximum force that all four segments could withstand. The criteria for setting the upper limit of each parameter was based on a benchmark where, at this maximum value, all sections from at least two of the three specimens remained unbroken.

5.1.1. Effect of Melting Time

According to Table 2, the range selected for the melting time spans from 6 to 10 seconds. It’s clear that a longer melting time allows polymers more time to establish stronger bonds. Table 3 presents the test outcomes for various melting times, specifically highlighting the number of samples that broke during testing. The values in this table range from 0 to 4, indicating the count of broken sections.

Table 3. Number of ruptures for different melting times.

Melting Time of Bottom Plate (°C)	Samples		
	1st	2nd	3rd
6	2	2	1
7	2	1	1
8	1	1	1
9	1	0	1
10	0	0	1

Figure 21 illustrates how welding strength fluctuates with changes in melting time, holding other parameters steady. Here, 'welding strength' refers to the average of the strength

values recorded across four segments of each sample. The data clearly indicate an increase in welding strength with longer melting times.

Figure 21. Variations in welding strength according to melting time.

5.1.2. Effect of Melting Temperature of Bottom Part

Table 4 presents the instances of sample fractures across a melting temperature range of 150 to 240 degrees Celsius. It's important to note that while samples exhibited cracks at all temperatures within this range, the count of sections experiencing weld separation varied with the temperature. Specifically, at 150°C, the welds in all four sections of the samples failed, while at 240°C, only one of the four sections in each sample fractured.

Table 4. Number of tears for different melting temperatures of bottom plate.

Melting Temp of Bottom Plate (°C)	Samples		
	1st	2nd	3rd
150	4	4	4
180	4	4	3
210	3	3	3
240	1	1	1
270	0	0	0

Table 4 clearly illustrates that a low melting temperature leads to inadequate melting of the bottom part, resulting in a suboptimal bond with the tube. It's important to consider that while increasing the bottom part's melting temperature might seem beneficial, it actually has a downside. Excessively high temperatures not only raise the power consumption of the hot plate machine but also cause over-melting of the bottom part. This over-melting enlarges the contact area between the tube and the bottom part, leading to a thinning of the melt base. Consequently, when torque is applied to join the bottom to the upper section, the weakened section is prone to breakage.

Figure 22 demonstrates the variation in welding strength with respect to the melting temperature of the bottom part, within the temperature range of 150 to 270 degrees Celsius. It is widely recognized that within this range, an increase in melting temperature correlates with enhanced weld performance.

Figure 22. Variations of welding strength according to the melting temperature of bottom part.

5.1.3. Effect of Melting Temperature of Tube

Table 5 presents the rupture patterns of the samples across a melting temperature spectrum of 190 to 270 degrees Celsius. The melting temperature range chosen for the tube differs markedly from that of the bottom part. This difference is attributable to the distinct materials composing the tube and the bottom part.

Table 5. Number of ruptures for different melting temperatures of tube.

Melting Temp of Tube (°C)	Samples		
	1st	2nd	3rd
190	3	4	3
215	3	3	3
240	2	2	2
255	2	1	1
270	1	0	0

Table 5 indicates that higher temperatures lead to improved weld quality. At 190°C, the bond between the bottom part and the tube is notably weak, allowing the tube to be detached from the bottom part with minimal force after the hot plate welding process. However, similarly to the melting temperature of the bottom plate, an excessively high melting temperature can create complications during the welding process. When the melting temperature of the tube exceeds a certain threshold, the tube may over-melt. Consequently, when torque is applied to join the tube to the bottom part, the force from the still-solid,

cooler portion of the tube transfers to the bottom part, resulting in what is known as cold welding. This phenomenon hinders the formation of a strong bond between the two parts, leading to failure in the back breaking test as the bucket becomes susceptible to breaking. Figure 23 illustrates how the welding strength varies with changes in the tube’s melting temperature.

Figure 23. Variations of welding strength according to the melting temperature of the tube.

5.2. Design of Experiment Method (DOE)

In this research, certain parameters were identified as experimental variables, and their varying ranges were

determined and input into Minitab software following the Design of Experiments (DOE) method. Utilizing this method, tests were suggested and executed, with the corresponding results recorded in the software. The final stage involved analyzing these results using Minitab, providing insights and optimizing both process and costs in the experimental framework.

For further investigation, we continued with the same parameters as in the previous phase: melting time, tube temperature, and bottom part temperature. However, the range selected for this study differs from that outlined in Table 2. The reason behind this change is that at the lower values of the chosen parameters, the weld becomes exceedingly weak, leading to virtually no bond between the bottom plate and the upper section. To maintain the connection quality between these two parts, we opted for a narrower range than the one presented in Table 2.

5.2.1. Design of Experiment Method (DOE)

Figure 24 reveals that within the range of 240 to 270 degrees Celsius, an increase in the tube’s melting temperature consistently leads to greater welding strength across all melting durations. Furthermore, an initial rise in melting time correlates with an expected increase in welding strength at every tube melting temperature. However, contrary to expectations, a continued increase in melting time results in a decline in the samples’ welding strength. It’s important to note that the peak strength value varies with each specific tube melting temperature.

Figure 24. The individual impacts of melting time and the tube’s melting temperature on the samples’ welding strength are distinct.

Figure 25 illustrates the combined effect of two parameters - the tube's melting temperature and the bottom part's melting temperature - on the welding strength of the samples. The graph indicates that the welding strength improves as the tube's melting temperature rises, applicable across all bottom part melting temperatures. Additionally, at varying tube melting

temperatures, the welding strength initially increases with the bottom part's melting temperature, but then diminishes beyond a certain point. Notably, the optimal welding strength is achieved at a bottom part melting temperature of 227 degrees Celsius, consistent across the three measured tube melting temperatures.

Figure 25. The individual impacts of the bottom plate melting temperature and the tube melting temperature on the welding strength of the samples are distinct.

Figure 26. Weld Strength Contours.

Figure 26.b displays the concurrent influences of the tube melting temperature and melting time on welding strength. It is evident that an increase in tube temperature significantly enhances welding strength, with the peak welding strength typically occurring between 9 and 9.5 seconds of melting time. Conversely, Figure 26.c indicates that the maximum welding strength is associated with the highest tube melting temperature; however, this relationship does not hold for the bottom plate melting temperature. It suggests that the most robust polymer bonds between the tube and bottom plate are formed around a melting temperature of approximately 225 degrees Celsius for the bottom plate.

Figure 27 presents a plate diagram depicting the impact of both the tube's melting temperature and the bottom part's melting temperature on welding strength. This three-dimensional representation clearly shows that the highest welding strength is reached at the tube's highest melting temperature.

Surface Plots of Strength

Figure 27. Plate diagram of the effect of all three welding parameters on welding strength.

The regression equation for welding strength Equation 12, considering various parameters, was derived using Minitab software. This equation correlates welding strength with several key factors, including the three primary parameters previously mentioned and their interactive effects.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Strength} = & -22520 + 787 \times \text{Melting Time} + 187.7 \times \text{Melting Temp of Bottom part} - 18.62 \times \text{Melting Temp of Tube} \\
 & - 43.27 \times \text{Melting Time}^2 - 0.3581 \times (\text{Melting Temp of Bottom Part})^2 \\
 & - 2.775 \times \text{Melting Time} \times \text{Melting Temp of Bottom Part} \\
 & + 2.362 \times \text{Melting Time} \times \text{Melting Temp of Tube}
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

5.2.2. DOE Optimization

Based on the laboratory results and analyses, we can estimate the optimum state to a certain degree. However, for a more precise determination of the optimal condition, we utilized the Minitab software’s Optimization feature. This approach yielded a more accurate result Table 6. The R-squared value for this equation was found to be 97%, indicating a highly satisfactory level of model accuracy.

Table 6. Optimization Solution.

Solution	MT	MTBP	MTT	SF	CD
1	9.2	226.3	270	257.6	1

MT-Melting Time, MTBP-Melting Temp of Bottom Part, MTT-Melting Temp of Tube, SF-Strength Fit, CD-Composite Desirability

The graphs presented in this article indicate that the optimal welding strength is achieved when the tube’s melting temperature reaches its peak at 270°C and the bottom part’s melting temperature is approximately 226.7°C, with a melting duration of 9.2 seconds. Under these conditions, the weld’s maximum strength is measured at 257.6 kg-force.

6. Conclusion

In this in-depth study, we have integrated theoretical perceptions with experimental results to increase the strength of welding in plastic cylinders. The theoretical discussion about the process, grounded in the reptation theory of polymer dynamics, provided a solid basis for understanding the molecular mechanisms that underlie the welding process. It stated the very critical role played by polymer chain mobility and diffusion in the interface regarding weld strength.

We experimentally studied the influence of the major welding parameters: melting temperature of the tube and bottom part, and melting time. This experiment confirmed the theoretical predictions, showing that:

1. Higher melting temperature and time enhance polymer chain diffusion, thereby enhancing the weld strength.
2. The optimal welding conditions, as determined through a detailed interaction effect analysis, represent a balance between enough thermal exposure to facilitate polymer interdiffusion and the avoidance of thermal degradation or too much fluidity of the polymer.

The research has further underscored the effectiveness of the Design of Experiments approach toward refining the settings of the parameters for the optimization of the welding process, as far as efficiency and strength results are concerned. This methodological approach not only ensured better accuracy in the experimentation but also gave a quantitative support to the theoretical predictions, thus placing the understanding of how different parameters affect the final weld quality on a comprehensive basis.

Finally, the current work contributes not only to the theoretical underpinning but also to the practical application of hot plate welding of plastic cylinders and forms a basis for further research in dynamic welding parameter interactions in other polymer manufacturing processes. The insights obtained here are poised to guide industrial applications, ensuring stronger and more reliable welds in manufactured products.

In the future, we plan to investigate additional parameters such as melting and welding pressure, delay time (the interval between the completion of melting and the start of welding), and thickness ratio (the ratio of the welding section thickness between the two parts to be joined). Another area of interest is simulating the welding process using Finite Element Modeling (FEM) to gain insights into the entire process before conducting experiments. Additionally, welding dissimilar materials presents unique challenges and will be a key focus of our future research.

Abbreviations

AM	Additive Manufacturing
CD	Composite Desirability
DOE	Design of Experiments
eCFR	Electronic Code of Federal Regulations
FEM	Finite Element Modeling
FW	Friction Welding
HDPE	High-Density Polyethylene
HPW	Hot Plate Welding
MT	Melting Time
MTT	Melting Temperature of Tube
MTBP	Melting Temperature of Bottom Part
OFAT	One-Factor-At-a-Time
PE	Polyethylene
PE	Polymer Extrusion
PP	Polypropylene
PS	Polystyrene

RF	Radio Frequency
SF	Strength Fit
WAXS	Wide-Angle X-ray Scattering

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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